

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS1.4.2

Fellows of second cohort have been recruited; revised Academy program has started

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Executive summary

Our second call for Academy Fellows resulted in 42 applications of early career scientists from various German universities or non-university research institutions. A selection committee composed of nine Earth System and Data Science experts chose 34 Fellows for our first Academy Cohort in a two-step selection procedure. First, each application was reviewed by five experts according to five scoring categories, including motivation, project ideas, skills and knowledge. Under consideration of the scoring results in step 1, the committee selected the most promising applicants in a panel discussion in step 2.

We are very thankful to the members of our scientific selection committee for their commitment and engagement: Denise Degen (RWTH Aachen), Henryk Dobslaw (GFZ Potsdam), Sabine Griebach (Jülich Supercomputing Centre), Dominik Hezel (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt), Miguel Mahecha (Universität Leipzig), Tobias Marke (Universität zu Köln), Jannes Münchmeyer (ISTerre Grenoble), Heiko Pälicke (MARUM/Universität Bremen), Anja Rösel (DLR), Timm Schöning (GEOMAR), Josefine Umlauf (ScaDS.AI/Universität Leipzig), Martin Werner (Technische Universität München) and Gerwin Wulf (Universität Bonn).

The Academy program for the second cohort started with our Kick-Off meeting on June 10th 2024. Till July 2024, we held two cohort calls. A list of the events with a short description is provided below. A description of the complete Academy program can be found on the NFDI4Earth website: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/academy/academy-program>

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1 List of Academy Fellows

- Aaron Hornschild (GFZ Potsdam)
- Aatralarasi Saravanan (United Nations University)
- Alexandra Runge (GFZ Potsdam)
- Amirhossein Ershadi (University of Tübingen)
- Angelos Mardiris (University of Potsdam)
- Anna Lara Simson (RWTH Aachen)
- Christian Riedel (University of Potsdam)
- Daria Pankova (University of Bonn)
- David Essing (Ruhr University Bochum)
- Farzaneh Sadeghi (Bochum University of Applied Science)
- Han Xiao (GFZ Potsdam)
- Jannis Hümmling (Alfred-Wegener-Institute AWI)
- Josepha Schiller (Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research ZALF)
- Juan Camilo Rivera Palacio (Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research ZALF)
- Lea Enguehard (Alfred-Wegener-Institute AWI)
- Liangjing Zhang (GFZ Potsdam)
- Louise Dädlow (University of Potsdam)
- Markus Münzinger (Leibniz Institute of Urban Ecology and Regional Development IOER)
- Nele Gloy (University of Potsdam)
- Nga Ying Lo (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)
- Nianhua Liu (Technical University Munich)
- Polina Tselykh (Constructor University)
- Samuel Mintah Ayim (University of Oldenburg)
- Sarah Klosterkamp (Goethe-University Frankfurt)
- Taís Maria Nunes Carvalho (University Leipzig)
- Theresa Sophie Boas (Forschungszentrum Jülich)
- Thoralf Dietrich (University of Potsdam)

- Tianqi Xiao (GFZ Potsdam)
- Umer Fiaz (Technical University Braunschweig)
- Vivien Grothe (University of Potsdam)
- Weimin Liu (MARUM Bremen)
- Yana Savytska (University of Tübingen)
- Yilak Kebede (Ruhr University Bochum)
- Zahra Zali (GFZ Potsdam)

2 Kick-off meeting 2024

From June 10th to June 12th, 2024, the second NFDI4Earth Academy cohort held its Kick-Off retreat in Potsdam. This event marked the first gathering of the 34 fellows, primarily focusing on networking and getting to know each other and the other's research.

The retreat featured flash talks where fellows presented their research topics, emphasizing the application of data science. These presentations served as a starting point for intra- and interdisciplinary discussions, exploring topic overlaps and potential collaborations. To foster a strong sense of community and ensure a positive, open, and safe environment, the group established guidelines for behavior and communication. Throughout various discussion sessions, fellows shared their ideas, expectations, and goals for the Academy. A key focus of these discussions was the content of courses and schools within the NFDI4Earth Academy program. The core areas of interest identified for future events include Machine/Deep Learning, Explainable and Trustworthy AI, Programming Skills, Statistical and Time Series Analyses, Satellite Data, and FAIR Data Management and Manipulation.

Evening activities, such as joint dinners and a GeoPubQuiz, further encouraged discussions and personal interactions. We thank all attending fellows for their valuable contributions and look forward to an exciting Academy program fostering both professional and personal growth and exchange.

3 Cohort Calls 2024

From the 03rd July till end of October 2024, the Academy Fellows will gather for five lecture series sessions, which each lasted 1-1.5 hours. In these participatory sessions, we explore open data science concepts, tools, and practical applications through exploring examples of research data management. The lessons aim to improve data workflows, increase efficiency, and showcase collaborative research projects. So far, two lectures have been conducted

Session 1 Wednesday 03.07. 10:00-12:00 am – No Fear of Data, an introduction to research data management (Ivonne Anders, DKRZ)

Session 2 Wednesday 10.07.2024 and Thursday 11.07.2024 09:00 am - 01:00 pm – Workshop on Version control, Git and GitLab (Tobias Schlauch, DLR & HIFIS)

The goal of the workshop was to introduce the Fellows to a powerful toolset to enhance their research software workflow. This Software Carpentry-style workshop was conceptualized as a two-half-day event that covered the basic tools required for a research software workflow: The Shell as a foundation for the following tools, employing Git as version control system (VCS) and using GitLab. Neither prior knowledge nor experience in those tools was needed. Participants were asked to read and follow the instructions on how to set up the tools for the workshop before the event.